

پاکستان میں خواتین کے اہم معاشرتی و سماجی مسائل اور ان کا شرعی حل
**SOCIAL ISSUES OF WOMEN IN PAKISTAN
AND THEIR SHARIA SOLUTIONS**

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ABSTRACT

Allah Almighty has bestowed upon Muslims the best family system. On the one hand, it gives due consideration to the human nature; and on the other hand, it has declared woman to be the custodian of the family system and Ummah identity. Sharia rules regarding the family system guarantee the success of married life. Since many provisions of Pakistani family law system do not fully comply with the Sharia rules, it has not been useful in resolving women's issues.

The article is aimed to briefly discuss important social issues of women and the problems faced by women due to complex judicial system and conflict with Islamic jurisprudence. The guiding principles of the Holy Qur'an regarding family issues and the unique family system of the Prophet's era and his companions have been highlighted.

Keywords: Family System, Social Issues, Sharia Rules, Women. Human Nature.

کلیدی الفاظ: خاندانی نظام، سماجی مسائل، شرعی احکام، خواتین، انسانی فطرت۔

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